

InvestCEC

Model and tools for urban/regional circular economy projects-Version 2

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1. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AIF	Alternative Investment Fund
CARTIF	Fundación CARTIF
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CE	Circular Economy
EIC	European Innovation Council
ESAC	European Super Angels Club
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
FAIF	Financial Alternative Investment Fund
G2G	Gate2Growth APS
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
SME	Small and Medium sized Enterprise
STW AG	Stadtwerke Klagenfurt Aktiengesellschaft
VENCAP	Venonaire Capital AG

2. Introduction

InvestCEC project

The circular economy (CE) is one of the core principles of the EU's Green Deal. One of the main challenges in advancing CE initiatives is securing funding. These projects are often classified as high-risk, either due to factors like technical immaturity, lack of track record, and uncertain market conditions.

Unlike businesses operating within traditional linear supply chains, those in the CE face a broader range of uncontrollable interdependencies. In the selection of candidates, it is crucial to assess their understanding of the unique risks and challenges these interdependencies present. It is important that the potential candidates have a full and thorough understanding of the special needs, challenges, and risks connected to this interdependency, which is often difficult to control, and therefore need to be adequately addressed in business plans. This is a critical pre-condition to be fulfilled before a case can be considered a potential investment case. Additionally, it is essential for candidates to demonstrate how their projects contribute to the CE in a way that is easily understandable by decision-makers at the city and regional levels.

Figure 1. Traditional vs. Circular economy supply chain

CE models differ significantly from traditional “take-make-dispose” systems, as they emphasize resources recovery, product life extension, and waste reduction. This shift requires an understanding of how value chains are interconnected and that businesses work collaboratively to close material loops and avoid resource leakage.

The success of CE projects is also highly dependent on regional and local factors, including the maturity of recycling infrastructure, the presence of effective public–private partnerships, and the level of citizen engagement. For this reason, CE business models must be context-sensitive, reflecting the geographical, socio-economic, and regulatory environments in which they operate. Key aspects such as material durability, product reparability and recyclability, and the availability of policy incentives for resource efficiency are all crucial in designing viable circular initiatives.

Model

The Horizon Europe project InvestCEC has developed a replicable model for initiating and financing CE projects in cities and regions. The model's purpose is to connect public authorities, entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers within a common framework that facilitates the creation of bankable, high-impact circular solutions. The approach was successfully tested in the City of Klagenfurt (Austria) and designed for replication across other European cities and regions.

This deliverable (D2.4) corresponds to Sub-task 2.1: Model Development, which focused on designing and integrating the different stages of the InvestCEC model, covering practices, methods, tools, and materials required to transform local needs into investment-ready projects.

Task 2.1 and Key Outcomes

Task 2.1.1 – Definition of Needs

The process began with the creation of a detailed *Needs Definition Document* in December 2022 (M2) to support cities and regions in identifying specific local challenges and opportunities for CE development. The main thematic areas initially identified by STW AG and VENCAP included GreenTech, Renewable Energy, Waste Management, and Smart City Logistics.

This document was revisited and refined in November 2024 (M25) by Stadwerke Klagenfurt AG (STW AG, public utility) and Gare2Growth (G2G, call manager), based on insights from the First Call for Entrepreneurs, which revealed *waste management* as the dominant priority theme among participants. Close cooperation between Stadwerke Klagenfurt AG and G2G proved essential to drafting the Second Call, as it ensured the selection process reflected real operational challenges and market opportunities.

For replication purposes, a standardised template was developed to help define urban and regional CE projects based on local needs. This template—first introduced in D2.1—is now also included in this deliverable (Section 3.2.1, p.14) and made publicly available via the InvestCEC website (Replication & Resources) and Zenodo community. It was additionally featured in a dedicated article (November 2024) titled “*Discover InvestCEC Templates and Promote Your Vision and Solutions for the Circular Economy*”, promoted across InvestCEC's communication channels and shared with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) representatives as a replicable tool for European cities.

After the closing of the calls, the applications were analysed by G2G, focusing on sectoral distribution, maturity stage, financing activity, and geographical coverage.

Task 2.1.2 – Selection Procedure

This task defined the criteria and process for selecting solution providers (small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) and entrepreneurs) able to address the identified city needs. Selection was based on three overarching categories: Fit for Purpose, Commercial Viability, and Innovation & Circularity. Each was supported by detailed sub-criteria to ensure transparency and replicability. Generic templates for both cities/regions and solution providers were developed to standardise data collection and enable structured comparison.

Task 2.1.3 – Investment Readiness

Led by G2G, this task focused on adapting already-developed tools and methodologies to help entrepreneurs and municipal partners prepare investment-ready business cases. The G2G Business Plan Tool, including an online writer, budget module, and self-assessment tool, was introduced and further tested during the project, but no particular requirement for model adaptation surfaced. Only few of the entrepreneurs responding on the two calls for entrepreneurs actually used the tools made available, most relied on own developed budgets. In the discussion with the entrepreneurs selected for interview and coaching, other more generic strategy issues, than financial modelling, became the focus for discussion. However, early in the process both public procurement barriers and problems connected to the often-identified fragility of many of the “circles” came into focus. This resulted in a deeper analysis of how these two problem areas could have a potential impact on funding of circular economy business cases. It was decided to address these problems in a special document to be finalized in connection with the final InvestCEC reporting. Given the market environment, registration of the fully prepared fund has been delayed pending a cornerstone LP, and the alternative tracks of the investment programme required additional time to be established or pending with the fund project. While deal flow was generated, the business cases were not immediately relevant and can be evaluated and supported later with regard to investment readiness.

Task 2.1.4 – Investment Programm

Under VENCAPs leadership, a dedicated EuVECA/AIF vehicle has been fully prepared to provide long-term financing for circular-economy ventures, to be launched once a cornerstone LP is secured. In parallel, the investment programme operates in a venture-partnership (“virtual fund”) mode that already enables joint diligence and co-investment with aligned partners. After fund establishment, this can be complemented by a crowd co-investment track via CONDA AG (together with the European Super Angels Club) to broaden participation by private investors and citizens.

Task 2.1.5 – Integration, Validation, and Replication

The final task consolidated all methodologies, templates, and tools into a coherent, replicable framework. It validated the model through the Klagenfurt demonstration, confirmed its transferability to other regional contexts, and documented best practices for future use. The resulting InvestCEC Model now serves as a standardised and adaptable pathway for cities and regions seeking to accelerate their CE transitions through structured planning, stakeholder collaboration, and innovative financing mechanisms.

erable

This deliverable presents and explains the **InvestCEC Model**, developed to support cities and regions in initiating, structuring, and financing CE projects. It provides a comprehensive description of the model’s concept and framework, detailed **guidelines for the implementation of each stage**, and specifies the **tools and materials** to be applied throughout the process.

The model is structured into **four interconnected stages**, each supported by practical instruments:

- **Stage 1 – Needs Definition:** A template designed to help cities and regions identify and describe their CE needs, priorities, and strategic objectives.
- **Stage 2 – Solution Identification:** A template for entrepreneurs and SMEs to present and describe their proposed CE solutions addressing the identified needs.
- **Stage 3 – Investment Readiness:** Guidelines and tools to support the preparation of business cases and business plans, ensuring that selected solutions are mature and credible for potential investors.
- **Stage 4 – Investment Programmeme:** Guidelines on how to apply and replicate the InvestCEC investment programmeme, including fund structures, investor engagement processes, and co-investment mechanisms.

Together, these four stages form a **replicable and adaptable framework** that connects local public needs with market-driven innovation and financing, thereby facilitating the effective implementation of CE solutions in cities and regions across Europe.

3. The developed model for circular economy projects

InvestCEC has developed and demonstrated a practical model that can support cities and regions in defining their needs and translating them into investable CE projects. The model's structured process enables public authorities to identify suitable solution providers (entrepreneurs and SMEs) capable of addressing municipal and regional priorities. Recognizing that financing gaps often hinder implementation, the InvestCEC model also provides entrepreneurs and SMEs with guidance to improve their investment readiness and access appropriate funding sources.

VENCAP has launched an integrated investment programme that combines a dedicated venture fund, co-investment pathways, and a crowd-based co-investment track via CONDA together with the European Super Angels Club. The programme is designed to translate municipal needs into bankable opportunities primarily through the InvestCEC venture capital vehicle: the EuVECA/AIF fund is fully prepared and can be established once a cornerstone LP is secured, while a "virtual fund" mode already enables joint diligence and co-investment today. Core venture partners include Una Terra and Universe Partners; in addition, the Carinthian Venture Fund (CVF) and a major electricity provider with its venture arm expand potential co-investment capacity. This coalition aligns with the investment thesis and allows solutions relevant to Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG (STW-AG) to be reviewed against real utility needs. Continuous, evidence-based feedback from STW-AG has refined the investment approach. The investment programme enables qualified opportunities to proceed to financing both ahead of first close and—after establishment of the InvestCEC Fund, with strong co-investor support and for later-stage opportunities that are large enough to engage effectively with a municipal utility.

The resulting model and accompanying support tools (InvestCEC Marketplace, Policy Instruments, Guidelines, and Manuals) are open-access and ready for replication in other cities and regions. Together, they provide a standardised, low-friction pathway for municipalities to identify needs, attract circular solutions, mobilise investment, and scale successful pilots across Europe.

These include:

1. *Guidelines to the establishment of a plan for circular economy transition based on the needs and objectives, assisting cities and regions to define the size and scope of the desired project, its vision and objectives, the strategies, and milestones for achieving these objectives, the potential challenges that should be overcome, the desired short-, mid- and long-term outcomes, and the estimated costs for the project's implementation (lead by STW AG).*
2. *Guide introducing to cities/regions different circular economy solutions available for various local settings and their potential benefits (lead by CARTIF).*

3. *Openly accessible resources, guidelines, and documentation for the optimization of the selection process*
4. *Guidelines on deal funnel procedures (lead by G2G).*
5. *Circular Economy Fundraising Guidebook (lead by VENCAP).*
6. *Guidebook explaining how to apply similar investment programme (lead by VENCAP).*
7. *Education and information material for Investors to create and raise awareness towards CE impact investments, building their confidence in CE investments and encouraging them to invest in such projects (lead by VENCAP).*
8. *Monitoring Investment Opportunities (led by VENCAP).*
9. *Public procurement was early in the project period recognized as a special barrier for the uptake of new and innovative solution delivered by early-stage SME. As a reaction to the Eu parliament resolution on Public Procurement in September 2025¹, this particular problem area has been addressed in a separate document.*

In the long term, these guidelines together with the accompanying support measures and practices will facilitate the replication of the InvestCEC model, thereby enhancing the sustainability and overall impact of the project's results.

STW AG recognises the importance of maximising the CE dimension in the solutions selected through the InvestCEC process. To complement its existing evaluation logic, STW AG developed an internal Circular Economy Assessment Framework (referred to as a "Score Card") to capture key elements of circular performance and ensure that circularity considerations are systematically integrated into project evaluations.

The Score Card was designed to reflect core principles such as resource efficiency, longevity, reuse, recycling, and waste minimisation, while considering operational realities such as cost efficiency and service reliability. STW AG acknowledges that under current financial and regulatory constraints, solutions demonstrating superior price-performance or supply/service security may, in some cases, outperform alternatives with higher circularity scores. Nevertheless, the integration of this structured circularity lens ensures that sustainability remains a central criterion in municipal decision-making.

During the InvestCEC demonstration, the Score Card was tested alongside VENCAP's Investor Check List, which is applied in evaluating business cases from a financial and investment-readiness perspective. The two tools were compared to ensure alignment between municipal and investor viewpoints, balancing environmental ambition with bankability and implementation feasibility.

The Circular Economy Score Card focuses on seven key dimensions:

1. **Resource Efficiency:** Efficient use of resources, minimisation of waste, and optimal lifecycle management, including dependency on renewable versus finite materials.
2. **Longevity and Durability:** Design for long service life, repairability, and modularity enabling maintenance and upgrades.

¹ European Parliament resolution of 9 September 2025 on public procurement (2024/2103(INI))

3. Reuse and Remanufacturing: Capacity for reuse, refurbishment, or remanufacturing of products, particularly within infrastructure systems.
4. Recycling and Material Recovery: Support for recycling and material recovery at end-of-life.
5. Minimisation of Waste and Pollution: Reduction of waste and emissions throughout the lifecycle and prevention of hazardous substances.
6. Measurement and Reporting: Mechanisms for monitoring and reporting circularity performance through defined metrics.
7. Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration: Degree of cooperation required among municipal, business, and citizen stakeholders, including behavioural readiness.

The Investor Check List used by VENCAP builds on these aspects but applies additional parameters relevant to investment decisions, such as team quality, market potential, product & business-model strength, technology, scalability and KPIs with a focus on practical utility fit, the level of circularity and value chain.

Testing and Outcomes

In the second half of the InvestCEC project, both the Score Card and the Check List were tested during the evaluation of selected cases. The exercise confirmed that the two approaches are complementary: STW AG's Score Card anchors municipal sustainability and integration priorities, while the Investor Check List captures financial viability and scalability. Together, they establish a shared evaluation logic that supports transparent, balanced decision-making between public and private partners—an important enabler for replication in other cities.

4. The InvestCEC model

The first stage of the model follows a structured process designed to help cities and regions identify their specific needs, screen for potential solution areas, and make an initial assessment of the costs required for a successful implementation. At this stage, municipalities and region are encouraged to prioritise sectors or value chains that present the highest potential for circular transformation. The identification of these needs in case of InvestCEC was further supported through dedicated workshop facilitated by STW and VENCAP, which guided team in defining priorities and shaping actionable pathways toward circular development.

The objective of these CE initiatives is to generate long-term benefits, such as enhanced sustainability, improved quality of life, cost efficiency, and better environmental performance. These expected impacts should be clearly defined and documented during this initial phase. The InvestCEC model also promotes inter-regional cooperation enabling neighboring cities and regions to jointly address shared challenges and co-develop circular and bioeconomy projects.

To support this process, InvestCEC has developed a set of guidelines and practical tools to assist municipal and regional authorities in planning and implementing CE transitions. Among these, STW AG, in collaboration with the consortium, prepared a *Guide for the Transition to a Circular Economy*. This guide provides a structured, step-by-step methodology that helps cities and regions to:

- **Define local needs and objectives** through baseline assessments of material flows, infrastructure, and socioeconomic factors;
- **Prioritize high-impact sectors** for circular transformation, ensuring that limited municipal resources are directed toward areas of greatest strategic and environmental potential;
- **Formulate strategies and milestones** that balance short-term “quick wins” with long-term systemic change;
- **Develop investment and financing approaches** suited to local capacities, including blended-finance models and public-private partnerships; and
- **Engage key stakeholders**—from municipal departments and local businesses to citizens and investors—through participatory workshops, training, and collaborative governance structures.

The guide also highlights decision-support tools (such as CE scorecards, material-flow analyses, and lifecycle assessment methodologies) that help quantify resource efficiency, identify bottlenecks, and track progress. Additionally, it provides templates for stakeholder mapping, risk-mitigation frameworks, and monitoring indicators,

enabling cities to align circular-economy goals with broader policy priorities like climate neutrality and social wellbeing.

By following this framework, cities and regions can create coherent circular transition plans that are context-specific, economically viable, and socially inclusive and turning pilot projects into scalable, investment-ready solutions that strengthen both urban resilience and regional cooperation.

In addition, CARTIF, together with consortium partners, produced the *Circular Economy Solution Areas for Urban and Regional Settings* guide. This resource supports cities and regions in identifying sectors and value chains with the greatest potential for circular transformation. It offers a practical overview of CE opportunities across key areas such as waste management, energy and resource efficiency, sustainable mobility, circular construction and urban development, and innovation in circular consumption and production.

The guide also highlights success cases from across Europe, such as Vienna's zero-waste strategy, Kalundborg's industrial symbiosis, and Graz's integrated mobility model and illustrates how circular principles can be applied in real contexts. By combining sector-specific insights with governance recommendations and policy references, the guide provides a valuable foundation for local authorities to design context-appropriate CE strategies.

Both resources are available as open-access materials on the InvestCEC project website and the InvestCEC Zenodo community and have been shared with the CCRI to support replication and broader uptake across Europe.

The second stage of the InvestCEC model focuses on the selection of solution providers (entrepreneurs, SMEs, or innovators) capable of delivering or further developing the CE solutions required by the participating city or region. This process builds upon the needs identified during the first stage and ensures alignment between municipal objectives, technological feasibility, and investment potential.

The selection procedure is multi-stakeholder oriented, taking into account the needs and conditions of cities and regions, the capabilities of entrepreneurs and SMEs, the priorities of investors, and the interests of local citizens and end-users. The aim is to ensure that selected solutions are not only technically and economically viable but also socially accepted and environmentally beneficial.

The **selection criteria** (see Section 3.2.1 of this deliverable) were developed collaboratively by the consortium to ensure transparency, comparability, and replicability. These include but are not limited to:

- **Fit-for-purpose and scalability** of the proposed solution in addressing identified local needs;
- **Demonstrated achievements or evidence of success**, including reference customers, investors, or proof-of-concept results;
- **Robust and sustainable business model**, with clear value propositions and potential for long-term impact;

- **Entrepreneurial and professional capacity** of the team to implement and scale the proposed solution;
- **Circularity and Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) performance**, as assessed through predefined indicators; and
- **Innovation and technological maturity**, ensuring the balance between novelty and readiness for deployment.

To facilitate replication of this stage in other local and regional contexts, InvestCEC developed a generic and replicable template for describing a city or region's needs, objectives, and required CE solutions. This standardized format supports comparability across regions and enables the systematic dissemination of identified high-priority needs to potential solution providers through the InvestCEC Marketplace and related communication channels.

In parallel, a complementary solution description template was created for entrepreneurs and SMEs wishing to submit proposals. This template captures all relevant information required for the selection process, including solution overview, circularity potential, business model, financing needs, and expected environmental and social impact. The overall process ensures a structured and transparent matching mechanism between public demand and private innovation supply. However, when digging deeper into this relation, "public procurement" and the potential "circle" fragility surfaced as special challenges, which had not been fully accounted to in the InvestCEC work programme. It resulted in a deeper analysis of how these two problem areas could have a potential impact on funding of circular economy business cases, and it was decided to address these problems in a special document to be finalized in connection with the final InvestCEC reporting². During the analysis to potential uptake of innovative solutions supplied by early stage SME's Public Procurement was identified both by SME's and by the Klagenfurt STW management as a barrier for which initiatives are required to get modified. This is fully in line with the observations in the EU parliamentary resolution on Public Procurement mentioned on page 12. The subject is further dealt with in a separate document.

4.2.1. TEMPLATE FOR CITIES/REGIONS

The purpose of this template is to collect and structure general information about the city or regions' vision, strategic targets, and planned initiatives related to CE development. It enables municipalities and regional authorities to define and communicate their priorities in a structured and comparable manner, facilitating a more effective matching process with SMEs and entrepreneurs offering relevant CE solutions.

By using this template, cities and regions can clearly express their needs, challenges, and opportunities for circular transition, while SMEs and entrepreneurs gain a comprehensive understanding of local priorities. This mutual transparency allows solution providers to propose tailored, investment-ready concepts that align with the city or region's overall strategy and development goals.

²Draft version" Circular Economy & Public procurement." October 2025

The template is structured in three main parts, reflecting a funnel-based logic that moves from broad visions to specific implementation opportunities:

1. **General Information** – Basic contextual data about the city or region, including demographic, economic, and environmental characteristics, key industrial sectors, and existing CE or sustainability initiatives.
2. **Overall Vision and Targets** – A description of the city or region’s long-term sustainability objectives, climate neutrality or waste-reduction targets, and cross-sectoral goals that guide the transition towards circularity.
3. **Concrete Projects and Planned Initiatives** – Details of specific CE projects, pilot actions, or areas of intervention. This section captures the city’s planned activities, expected impacts, and any technical or financial needs that could be addressed through collaboration with SMEs or entrepreneurs.

Each section of the template encourages the inclusion of information about how the proposed or ongoing projects contribute to CE principles, such as resource efficiency, reuse, recycling, and the regeneration of natural systems. Cities and regions are also invited to indicate their preferred collaboration models, expected investment scale, and potential funding mechanisms (e.g., public–private partnerships, EU instruments, or local funds).

The use of this standardized template ensures consistency across different cities and regions, thereby simplifying the process of collecting and analysing data within the InvestCEC Marketplace and enhancing the visibility of local CE opportunities.

Table 1. Template for cities/regions

GENERAL INFORMATION	
City/Municipality	
Location (region it is part of)	
Name of municipal organization	
Please provide links to city websites for more information	
GENERAL VISION, TARGETS & STRATEGIES	

<p>VISION</p> <p>What is the circular economy vision of your city/region</p>	
<p>TARGETS</p> <p>What targets have been set to work to follow this vision</p>	
<p>STRATEGIES</p> <p>What measures and strategies have been set to achieve these targets</p>	
<p>Other measures discussed</p>	
<p>STRENGTHS</p> <p>Regional Strengths and resources available</p>	
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>What resources are less present and could serve to realize the city's circular economy vision</p>	

<p>CIRCULAR ECONOMY ACHIEVEMENTS</p> <p>Do you have any existing or past examples of circular economy projects or initiatives in your city/region?</p>	
PLANNED PROJECT 1	
<p>Project NAME</p>	
<p>LEAD person to contact</p>	
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Project Description</p>	
<p>TASKS</p> <p>Projects actions/tasks</p>	
<p>BUDGET</p>	
<p>STAKEHOLDERS</p> <p>Who are the stakeholders and actors in this project, what are their role</p>	

<p>RESSOURCES</p> <p>Strengths of project: actors, technology</p>	
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>Missing elements / actors / technology/ supply chain</p>	
<p>MIRROR PROJECTS</p> <p>Examples of eventual successful similar/inspiring solutions</p>	
<p>CIRCULARITY</p> <p>How does the solution in question qualify as circular? E.g.:</p> <p><u>“Eliminates waste and pollution”</u></p> <p><u>“Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)”</u></p> <p><u>“Regenerate nature”</u></p>	

BUTTERFLY DIAGRAM

Does the solution's value chain operate on the technical or biological side of the butterfly diagram? (explain)

4.2.2. TEMPLATE FOR ENTREPRENEURS

The purpose of this template is to enable SMEs and entrepreneurs to propose innovative CE solutions based on the needs and priorities defined by cities and regions in the previous template (Section 3.2.1). The template provides a structured framework for collecting initial descriptions of proposed solutions, allowing for an informed and transparent first-round selection of the most promising cases to advance to the next stage of the InvestCEC model—investment readiness and validation.

The templates have in other EU projects, and when coaching individual companies in business strategy development been validated. During the InvestCEC project only few of the entrepreneurs responding to the two calls for entrepreneurs indicated that they had used the structure in the templates to present or clarify their business strategy. The majority relied on own already developed structures. In the discussion with the entrepreneurs selected for interview and coaching, other more generic strategy issues became the focus for discussion.

The template is designed to ensure comparability across submissions and to capture the information necessary for evaluating solutions according to the main InvestCEC selection criteria. It is divided into **three main parts**, corresponding to the key dimensions of the selection process:

1. **Solution and Value Chain Description** – A concise presentation of the proposed solution, including its concept, target application area, market relevance, and alignment with the specific needs identified by the city or region. This section also requests information about the value chain involved, key partners, and potential customers or end-users.
2. **Development Stage and Requirements** – A description of the current maturity level of the solution (e.g. concept, prototype, demonstration, or commercial stage), the technical and financial resources required for implementation, and any regulatory or operational barriers that may need to be addressed. This part also allows proposers to indicate specific collaboration or co-investment needs.

3. **Degree of Innovation and Circularity** – An assessment of how the solution contributes to CE principles, including aspects such as resource efficiency, waste reduction, reuse or recycling potential, and environmental impact. The section also highlights the innovative aspects of the business model, technology, or process, and explains how these contribute to creating long-term sustainability and economic value.

This structure reflects the **three principal criteria** applied during the InvestCEC selection process:

1. **Fit with the city or region’s needs;**
2. **Commercial viability of the business case, value chain, and entrepreneurial team;** and
3. **Degree of innovation and integration of CE principles.**

The use of this standardized template ensures that proposed solutions are presented in a clear, comparable format that facilitates the joint evaluation process by municipal, technical, and investment experts. It also supports the creation of a shared knowledge base of CE solutions, accessible through the InvestCEC Marketplace and related dissemination tools.

Outcome and Application

The template was tested during the InvestCEC demonstration in Klagenfurt, where it, for a few cases, proved effective in standardising solution proposals and facilitating dialogue between entrepreneurs, investors, and municipal stakeholders. This structured approach simplified the evaluation process, enhanced transparency, and helped identify solutions with both strong circular potential and investment readiness. However, most of the other cases had not reached a maturity level where the use of the model would add value.

The final version of the SME/Entrepreneur template is available as an open-access resource on the InvestCEC website and within the InvestCEC Zenodo community, enabling replication in other European cities and regions engaging in CE transitions. However, the full practical use of the template for projects, which involve public sector cooperation, requires further development to fully address the barriers connected to public procurement and the potential revision of some of the public procurement requirements with are expected to be implemented following the European Parliaments September 2025 resolution on Public procurement³.

Table 2. Template for entrepreneurs

COMPANY INFO	
NAME	

³ European Parliament resolution of 9 September 2025 on public procurement (2024/2103(INI))

LOCATION	
WEBSITE	
FIELD Please describe your general expertise and current operations	
ACHIEVEMENTS	
YOUR SOLUTION	
NAME	
DESCRIPTION Please provide a short description of your project/solution	
VALUE CHAIN Describe the value chain of your solution	
STAKEHOLDERS Please list the stakeholders, their roles, and interests	

<p>YOUR ROLE</p> <p>What is your role in this project and value chain?</p>	
<p>STRENGTHS</p> <p>Please describe the strengths of your solution to meet the needs identified by the municipality/region. What do you think will make it successful?</p>	
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>Are there any missing elements, or elements that could be strengthened to better meet the needs identified by the municipality/region?</p>	
DEVELOPMENT STAGE	
<p>PROGRESS</p> <p>Please describe the current state of development of your solution</p>	

<p>FINANCIAL NEEDS</p> <p>Please provide an estimate of the investments needed to bring your solution to maturity</p>	
<p>TIMELINE</p> <p>How long would it take to develop and deploy your solution?</p>	
INNOVATION & CIRCULARITY	
<p>REFERENCE PROJECTS</p> <p>Have you or any of the partners created/participated in other similar projects? Are you inspired by any other projects?</p>	
<p>INNOVATION</p> <p>How does your solution differ from existing solutions?</p>	
<p>CIRCULARITY</p> <p>How does the solution in question qualify as circular? E.g.:</p>	

<p><u>“Eliminates waste and pollution”</u></p> <p><u>“Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)”</u></p> <p><u>“Regenerate nature”</u></p>	
<p>BUTTERFLY DIAGRAM</p> <p>Does the solution’s value chain operate on the technical or biological side of the butterfly diagram? (explain)</p>	

4.2.3. SELECTION CRITERIA

The following criteria can serve as overall guidelines for cities and regions to assess and select CE solutions and SMEs or entrepreneurs proposing them. Using these criteria on solutions that demonstrate clear investment needs and potential can then proceed to the next stage of the InvestCEC model which is Investment Readiness. The selection process proposed is built **around three overarching categories, each** detailed with a set of sub-criteria. These criteria can also serve as guidance for SMEs and entrepreneurs when preparing their proposal templates to ensure comparability, transparency, and alignment with municipal needs.

A. FIT FOR PURPOSE: Evaluates how well the proposed solution responds to the identified needs of the city or region and its capacity to deliver measurable local benefits.

- **Fit with city/region needs:** Relevance of the solution to the defined priorities and challenges identified in the city/region template.
- **Value added:** Expected impact in terms of sustainability, service improvement, or efficiency gains.
- **Needs addressed:** Clarity on which specific issues or barriers the solution aims to solve (e.g., waste management, energy efficiency, resource recovery, mobility, or construction).

B. COMMERCIAL VIABILITY: Assesses the business and operational feasibility of the proposed solution, including the strength of the company, the soundness of its value chain, and its potential for long-term market success.

- **Company profile and team:** Experience, expertise, and operational capacity of the entrepreneur or SME.
- **Past achievements and success indicators:** Proven track record, traction, customer base, or presence of investors.
- **Value chain viability:** Robustness and coherence of the proposed business model, including key partners and market positioning.
- **Stakeholder alignment:** Extent to which the interests of involved partners (public, private, and investors) are consistent and mutually beneficial.
- **Cost–benefit balance:** Proportionality between the resources required for implementation and the expected value created (economic, environmental, and social).

C. INNOVATION & CIRCULARITY: Examines the novelty, scalability, and contribution of the proposed solution to CE principles.

- **Degree of innovation:** Extent to which the solution introduces new technologies, processes, or business models compared to existing alternatives.
- **Added value across the value chain:** Demonstrated benefits to multiple stages of production, consumption, and resource recovery.
- **Circularity performance:**
 - *Technical dimension:* Durability, reparability, modularity, and ability to maintain value throughout the product or service lifecycle.
 - *Biological dimension:* Level of regeneration, biodegradability, or contribution to restoring natural systems.
 -

Following a delayed cornerstone commitment for the InvestCEC EuVECA/AIF, VENCAP pursued an alternative financing pathway built on venture partnerships (“virtual fund”). After testing several fundraising routes (cornerstone-first, fund-of-funds, and targeted strategic LPs), VENCAP designed and finalized an alternative venture-partnership (“virtual fund”) pathway. Standing up this coalition and co-investment mechanics with VC partners and strategic investors—required additional legal and operational work, so it reached a ready-to-run state only toward the end of the project. The framework is now fully prepared and operationally clear, but it has not yet been used to execute an investment. In the interim, deal flow was curated and monitored so that qualified cases can move via partner co-investment under the venture-partnership track and through the InvestCEC AIF/EuVECA vehicle once established.

ness

The following section describes the tools that were made available to entrepreneurs and SMEs with identified funding needs, who were invited to participate in the **InvestCEC Investment Readiness process** (Task 2.1.3). The objective of this stage is to strengthen the capacity of selected entrepreneurs to develop **investment-ready business cases**, enabling them to attract private and/or public financing and effectively engage with investors and

funding institutions. several companies engaged with VENCAP in general — not all of them clearly entering an investment readiness process, but they asked questions and expressed willingness to stay in touch and share updates on their developments. Examples include Istya, Terra Green, Aquaturea, CRAB Traceability Systems, Concular, VCG AI, MyPilz, Protovation, GreenGrow, RUTENA, WASTICS, Ekotekt, ChargeandMore and CircularFabrics⁴.

A central element of this process is the use of the **G2G Business Plan Tool**⁵, which was made available for entrepreneurs responding to the InvestCEC project calls for entrepreneurs. The tool is designed to guide entrepreneurs from the idea stage to a **viable and credible business model**, providing both methodological and practical support in the preparation of professional business plans.

The G2G Business Plan Tool validated in other EU projects consists of the following components:

A. Online Business Plan Writer Tool

An interactive online platform that supports entrepreneurs in structuring and drafting their business plans. The tool provides a step-by-step process covering all key business components, including value proposition, market analysis, operations, financials, and risk assessment.

B. Budget Module

A dedicated financial planning component that enables users to create detailed budgets, forecasts, and cash-flow projections. This module ensures that financial assumptions are coherent, transparent, and aligned with the expectations of potential investors.

C. Business Plan Self-Assessment / Quality Assessment Tool

An integrated evaluation tool that allows entrepreneurs to assess the completeness, consistency, and investment readiness of their business plans. It helps identify gaps and areas for improvement before presenting the case to investors or applying for funding.

This online tool provides a clear and structured framework that covers all essential aspects of a business model. It enables entrepreneurs to transform a conceptual business idea into a comprehensive business plan by systematically working through each section of the tool and evaluating the viability, coherence, and credibility of their business strategy.

All three components are important when creating a business plan for a product or service. **Component A** ensures that the business model has a narrative and that all relevant areas are thoroughly explained in written text. **Component B** strengthens the financial background of the business plan and as a result, secures that the visions and assumptions in the business plan are compared and converted into monetary terms. For the system, it is not necessary to fill in both Component A and B for evaluation (C), however, it is strongly advised the business plan will

⁴ This list is not necessarily complete, as several contacts were made through direct phone calls over time. Promising applicants remain in the curated pipeline.

⁵ The Gate2Growth on-line business plan tool was developed and validated during other EU projects. Smaller adaptation takes place when being re-used.

only be ready for the market and investors when the written text is reflected in numbers as well. The outcome of using the G2G Business Plan Writer Tool is a complete, coherent business plan supported by a detailed and consistent budget overview that provides a solid foundation for presenting the business case to potential investors or funding partners.

The intent behind the tool is to assist interested entrepreneurs in determining how their solution/CE project could be realistically implemented into their own business strategy. The tool can be helpful for business owners of all levels of expertise, both seasoned, as well as those with little to no prior business plan writing skills. The tool is self-guided, meaning that the user can go through the different sections and fill in the required details without external help or guidance. Ensuring all components and relevant concerns related to a business plan are defined, potential difficulties addressed, and fundamental assumptions supported are recognised as a challenge when creating businesses and plans.

Using a unique approach, based on G2G's extensive experience as a strategic advisor on business development and access to funding and financing, the G2G Business Plan Writer is designed to help connect the many elements of starting a new business and receive quality feedback on it. This way, the tool offers basic support for the business plan writing process and thus helps the entrepreneurs to put their plans into action and make their idea a reality. Once the business plan is completed, it can be used to steer a company's strategy, presented to investors, or included as an annex in a grant application. Additionally, the budget module and the written business plan together can be used to create a compelling narrative about the business perspective for meetings with business associates, investors, banks, or other financial organizations, increasing the chance of getting funded or receiving attractive investment opportunities. The lack of "business history or lack of track record" is often an issue that young or recently founded companies must overcome, and a well-written, comprehensive business plan is potentially a solution for that challenge. One of the biggest finance accounting services, PwC, also highlighted in a recent Start-up evaluation report *that companies without historical financial data or proof of concept can counteract this perceived weakness with a strong, thorough market and business strategy. With a clearly defined business plan, it is more likely that investors and potential key partners will see the value and investment/partnership opportunity in the company* (PwC News, 2021). However, late in the InvestCEC project barriers created the Public Procurement requirements surfaced as a special not well recognized problem. Therefore efforts were during the last months of the InvestCEC project allocated to conduction a deeper analysis of this potential barrier. The results will be summarized in a special document Circular Economy & Public procurement⁶.

A. The online business plan writer

Users can select a predefined or customized template to start their business plan. Both templates include all the elements needed to structure a final business plan.

⁶ Draft version: Circular Economy & Public procurement October 2025

The advantage of the customized template is that the user can make their own structure and/or rearrange the elements to fit their needs, e.g., if the product cannot be protected, the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) section can be taken out (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Screenshot of creating a customized template

The predefined template is sectioned into 5 main areas that overall consist of 25 writing elements (explained in detail later). The predefined template is a safe choice for all as it has been structured to include all relevant elements of a business plan and thus ensures that all key points are covered and explained (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Predefined template with the 25 elements and an enlarged example of Chapter 2

The content and structure of the writing part include findings from real-life cases and relevant business theories. The five main sections, namely Business model; Customers and Market; Product and Competition; Management and Budget are inspired by the book “How to attract investors” (Bundgaard-Jørgensen, 2016) illustrated in Figure 4.

The 25 elements to be completed focus on identifying the following five main areas:

1. *Business model, Sales & Marketing partners*
2. *Customer, Customer needs, Market*
3. *Product, Competition, Production, Key resources*
4. *“Make it all work”, Management*
5. *Budget, Funding, Investor Osterwalder’s “Business Model Canvas” methodology⁷, also influenced the structure and the description of the elements of the tool (Error! Reference source not found.).*

Figure 4. The 5 main areas of a business plan from the book “How to attract investors”

⁷ “Business Model Generation” (Osterwalder et al., 2010),

Figure 5. The 9 elements of the Business Model Canvas

The elements focusing on the identification of customer needs and business model development are also inspired by the findings in the book “Blue Ocean Strategy”⁸. The authors emphasize that it is crucial to analyze and understand how and why a new product, solution, or service is better equipped to satisfy customer needs than other products, solutions, or services currently on the market. The instructions in the online business plan writer are meant to support such analyses and the consideration of customers' actual needs in a competitive strategy.

B. The budget module

The budget module in the G2G online business plan tool is closely connected to the writing part. Although it is not compulsory to fill out, it is recommended to strengthen the business plan in the making. This optional module will allow the user to forecast 24 months + 5 years of cost and revenue, and this serves as a strengthening addition to the business plan. The reason behind planning for this specific period is to help companies see potential liquidity challenges. For some (mostly young) companies liquidity planning is essential in the short term, as such, they need to be able to plan for costs in the actual month it occurs and not only have it on a yearly average (as is done beyond the initial 24 months). The lifespan of investment funds and investment horizon is typically between 7-10 years, so the forecast used in the Budget module corresponds to said requirements.

It has a similar layout to the G2G Business Plan Writer, as the user is able to get an overview of the necessary steps and see progress. A significant difference with the budget module is that its elements have a defined order that has to be followed while filling in and elements are disabled until the previous ones are filled in (7). This is because the calculated financial information is heavily dependent on the numbers submitted by the user.

⁸ Blue Ocean Strategy. W. Chan Kim & Renee Mauborgne, 200.

Figure 6. Overview of the Budget module elements (mock-up)

C. Business Plan self-assessment

This last part of the tool is inspired by the H2020 SME Instrument (now European Innovation Council (EIC) Accelerator) evaluation principles created by the European Commission, but it has been modified to be used for commercial business plans. It is formed around the 25 elements (also used for the Online business plan writer (A)) that should be covered in a typical business plan to help the entrepreneur determine how complete the plan is and, ultimately, whether it is investor-ready or not.

The Quality assessment tool provides a structured approach to the evaluation process. Each of the 25 components addressed in the business plan must be scored on "completeness & quality" by the evaluator. It is possible to skip scoring factors that are unimportant in the actual context. The basis for the "total quality scoring" results is altered if a step in the scoring procedure is skipped.

In addition to the official scoring of each component, comments may be added if the evaluator considers them relevant. The "Business Plan quality assessment tool" translates the final scoring/assessment into clear and thorough written feedback that is delivered to the entrepreneur when the evaluation process is complete. Moreover, the user also gets a color-coded overview of the template and its elements (Figure 8), where "green" means that content is relevant, "yellow" indicates that the content needs to be improved, and where the evaluator does not find the content relevant or is missing, "red" will be chosen. Thus, the user will also get a visual representation of the progress of the business plan.

Figure 7. Overview over the scoring page for each of the 25 elements in the business plan

amme

This stage operationalises financing for circular-economy projects through an architecture that is both ready for fund establishment and already usable via partner co-investment.

The dedicated InvestCEC EuVECA/AIF is prepared: Under Venionaire Capital’s leadership, a European Venture Capital vehicle has been fully prepared to provide early-stage and growth capital to utility-ready circular solutions. Formal registration will be launched once a cornerstone LP is secured. The fund’s documentation set (all legal registration documents, Investment Focus & Fund Facts, Pitch Deck, LP Questionnaire/subscription set, governance/compliance) and impact instrumentation are in place and aligned with project materials.

The Venture-Partnership Model (“virtual fund”) is ready: In parallel, the programme can already operate through a venture-partnership model that enables joint screening, diligence, and co-investment with aligned managers and strategic investors. The core venture partners include Una Terra (early-growth impact) and Universe Partners (resilience tech), with additional strategic capacity from the Carinthian Venture Fund (CVF) and a major electricity provider with its venture arm. This coalition expands ticket flexibility, sector coverage, and follow-on strength, allowing qualified cases to move forward ahead of—and later alongside—the InvestCEC AIF’s first close.

Crowd co-investment track (at fund go-live): After fund establishment, a crowd-based co-investment channel via CONDA (with the European Super Angels Club) could broaden participation to private investors and citizens on a deal-by-deal basis.

How opportunities flow into financing: Sourcing is fed by the two Calls for Entrepreneurs and Venionaire’s pan-European deal flow. Short-listed teams enter a standardised investment-readiness (IR) pathway (deck, driver-based model and a concise impact/ESG snapshot aligned with guidance). Solutions mapped to STW-AG needs (waste, smart city logistics, renewable energy, green tech & sustainability) and assessed for utility deployability. Aligned cases can be reviewed with venture partners for joint diligence and potential co-investment.

Standards, transparency, and impact: The programme embeds circular-economy criteria and ESG/impact indicators into screening and due diligence and provides practical guidance for portfolio management and impact monitoring. The resulting framework—templates, scorecards, and reporting outlines—supports replication by giving cities, regions, and investors a transparent, comparable basis for decisions.

What this enables: Even before the fund's first close, the venture-partnership model ensures that promising, utility-aligned solutions could progress.

Figure 8. Outline of the stages of the investment programme

The InvestCEC Fund Project should apply a harvesting strategy within the fund's operational framework. The implementation period is designed to span approximately eight years, following a structured cycle that includes an initial investment phase of up to three years, focused on deploying capital into local CE projects and followed by a growth and value-creation phase of around five years, and concluding with a divestment phase of approximately three years. This approach ensures sufficient time for portfolio companies to mature, generate measurable circular and financial returns, and enable the reinvestment or reallocation of capital in alignment with the fund's long-term CE objectives.

4.4.1. GUIDES TO DEFINE AN INVESTMENT FOCUS

To enable replication of this stage in other local and regional contexts, a set of guidelines and methodological steps has been prepared.

Step 1: Detailed market analysis

A comprehensive market analysis provides an overview of **startups, SMEs, and investors** active in the CE domain. This analysis helps identify market gaps, active innovation clusters, and potential investment opportunities. Startups can be assessed based on the following criteria:

- *Industry/Category*
- *Age*
- *Funding Amount and stage (based on investment rounds)*
- *Business model description (short qualitative overview)*
- *Geographical location of HQ*
- *Current investors and co-investment network*

All startups can then be classified according to the following sectors of the CE:

- *Greentech & Sustainability*
- *Renewable Energy*
- *Smart City Logistics*
- *Waste Management*
- *Other emerging circular domains.*

Step 2: Define relevant categories

Based on the **needs assessment** carried out during the earlier stage of the InvestCEC model, relevant categories should be defined in accordance with the **specific priorities, challenges, and industrial structure** of the local or regional context. This ensures that investment activities remain focused on sectors where CE initiatives can deliver the highest environmental and socioeconomic impact.

Step 3: Define cooperation opportunities with SMEs/startups

This step focuses on mapping **potential cooperation pathways** between local authorities, SMEs, and startups. The goal is to explore how innovative businesses can contribute to addressing identified urban or regional needs, thereby creating **added value through new circular business models and partnerships**. Such collaboration can include technology co-development, pilot demonstrations, joint ventures, or public–private partnerships.

Step 4: Define evaluation criteria

To assess potential business cases and identify investment-ready opportunities, **market-standard evaluation criteria** are applied. These criteria help determine the attractiveness, feasibility, and scalability of each proposal:

- *Team: Expertise and experience of the team as well as successful internal collaboration and complementary skills.*
- *Market: Size and dynamics of the market, growth potential, competitor analysis.*

- *Product/Product-Market Fit: validation of the product concept in the target market and differentiation of the product from competitors or similar products in the market.*
- *Value Proposition, the extent to which the product is needed by the customer - in the specific case also whether the product meets STW's criteria.*
- *Scalability: ability to expand a business model*
- *Technology: stability and progress of the technology and its scalability.*
- *Financials and KPIs: Traceability of business plan, return on investment, cash flow.*

This structured, four-step process ensures that local and regional investment programmes are designed systematically, combining data-driven market insight with strategic alignment to regional needs and robust evaluation criteria. The resulting methodology is replicable across European regions, enabling the creation of coherent investor ecosystems that foster scalable, high-impact CE ventures.

4.4.2. TEMPLATE FUND QUESTIONNAIRE

The purpose of this template is to provide information from the investors. This questionnaire captures core parameters of the fund to support scoping, service-provider onboarding, and LP pre-screening. It standardises information on structure (AIF/EuVECA, legal form, duration), economics (target size, fees, share classes), operations (depository, auditor, valuation/reporting cadence), and governance/compliance. Collecting consistently, it can prepare advisors to draft documents efficiently, allows potential LPs to assess high-level fit, and a clear audit trail for regulatory purposes.

Table 3. Template fund questionnaire

PROPOSED PARTIES	
Proposed portfolio manager	
Proposed depository	
Proposed auditor (if any)	
Proposed advisors	
BASIC FUND INFORMATION	

Proposed name of the investment fund	
Fund type (respective law, e.g. AIF, UCITS)	
Legal Type (e.g. SICAV)	
Is the fund a single fund or an umbrella fund?	
Expected Fund volume	<p>On first issue:</p> <p>After 12 months:</p> <p>After 24 months:</p>
Duration of the fund	<input type="checkbox"/> Unlimited <input type="checkbox"/> Limited (..... years)
Open or Closed	<input type="checkbox"/> Open-ended <input type="checkbox"/> Closed-ended
In case of an open-ended structure, what are the redemption cut-off dates/exit restrictions to be implemented?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 day <input type="checkbox"/> 1 week <input type="checkbox"/> 1 month <input type="checkbox"/> 6 months <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
The reference currency of the fund	
Appropriation of income	<input type="checkbox"/> Reinvesting <input type="checkbox"/> Distribution
Share classes	Number of share classes (per segment, if multiple):
If multiple share classes, please provide guidance on the proposed differences	
Initial Issue price in the reference currency	
Subscription minimum in reference currency	

Valuation frequency	<input type="checkbox"/> Annually <input type="checkbox"/> Semi-annually <input type="checkbox"/> Monthly <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Accounting year-end	<input type="checkbox"/> 31 st Dec <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Subscriptions in kind? (If yes, please specify)	

5. Worked example: The case of Klagenfurt am Wörthersee

Challenges of the city of Klagenfurt am Wörthersee

The vision of the smart city of Klagenfurt am Wörthersee is to create an emissions-neutral, energy-efficient, and resource-conscious urban environment that ensures a high quality of life while fostering responsible citizenship.

Following a municipal council resolution adopted on May 25th 2021⁹ the climate strategy's objectives of Klagenfurt were fixed by reducing 70% CO₂ by 2030 and reducing 90% CO₂ by 2050. Due to the successful reduction in emissions, the overarching target of reducing emissions by 90% by 2050 has been brought forward to 2040. Since April, 2022, the city has been the only Austrian representative to participate in the EU's "100 climate-neutral and smart cities" mission, further strengthening its climate commitments.

Participation in the EU Cities Mission prompted the adoption of even more ambitious climate targets within the city's Smart City climate strategy, aiming for climate neutrality by 2030 (with 81% of reductions achieved directly and 19% through offsetting measures). This strategic orientation is now being implemented through comprehensive measures across nine fields of action: Mobility, Energy, Infrastructure, Economy, Nature and Living Spaces, Urban Development, Governance, Digitalisation, and Generations. A total of 236 measures were developed by 59 experts across these thematic working groups, coordinated by a core team from the City of Klagenfurt, Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG (STW AG), and external organisations.

It quickly became clear that the required investments in large-scale sustainable projects could not be financed solely by municipal resources. The funding of high-risk CE initiatives presents significant challenges for the public sector, particularly due to the Maastricht criteria, which limit municipal debt levels. Consequently, the city and STW AG identified the need for a blended financing approach, combining public support, guarantees, and private co-investment. In this context, the potential of fund-based financing was explored to facilitate participation by start-ups and innovative SMEs.

To demonstrate the InvestCEC model in Klagenfurt am Wörthersee, the project aligns directly with the city's goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by at least 90% by 2030 through increased renewable energy use and enhanced circularity in key waste management sectors. The demonstration focuses on three main material and energy streams:

⁹https://www.klagenfurt.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Stadt_Klagenfurt/01-StadtSERVICE/Klima-Umwelt/Smart_City_Strategie/Smart_City_Klimastrategie_V7.1_ENGL_240716.pdf

- **Wastewater and Sewage Sludge** – Construction of a sewage sludge incineration plant adjacent to the city’s wastewater treatment facility. The plant will generate waste heat for district heating and enable nutrient recovery. The resulting ash and digestate will be hygienised for use as **fertiliser** by local farmers and private users.
- **Biogenic Waste** – Development of a new organic waste treatment plant with a processing capacity of approximately 15,000 tonnes per year. Klagenfurt currently generates around 9,000 tonnes of organic waste annually, with an additional 3,000 tonnes collected from surrounding municipalities. The plant will produce approximately 1.4 million m³ of biogas, 4,000 tonnes of compost, and 500 m³ of liquid fertiliser annually.
- **Residual, Plywood, and Furniture Waste** – Expansion of waste-to-energy and power–heat coupling processes to increase energy efficiency and circular material recovery.

These sectors served as the starting point for Klagenfurt’s participation in InvestCEC and the definition of its local needs. The city’s objective was not only to improve the sustainability of specific facilities but also to use these infrastructure projects as catalysts for broader systemic change. By linking ongoing developments—such as the modernisation of wastewater and organic-waste treatment—with innovative investment and cooperation models, Klagenfurt aims to demonstrate how public utilities can act as drivers of urban circular transition.

Innovation is essential for developing solutions for the transformation towards a CE. One of the major challenges in this process is securing adequate funding, which often acts as a barrier to the development of innovative solutions and the progression of the CE. Examples are the optimisation or replacement of outdated plants, but also the modernisation of existing methods and technologies. If the funding is not provided through public sources, securing investment from private investors becomes crucial for project success. However, attracting such investment requires presenting business cases that demonstrate the potential for an acceptable, risk-adjusted return on investment, comparable to other available investment opportunities.

Overview of the Market Startups and Investors

To gain an overview of potentially relevant companies providing “circular economy” solutions, VENCAP has prepared a detailed analysis of the companies as the first step towards the current market overview of startups and investors active in the CE. The research approach selected was to conduct an analysis and to drill down on secondary data of active Ventures, and their respective Investment Rounds and Investors, obtained from Crunchbase. In total, 680 companies remained after cleaning the data based on several criteria to keep the data as relevant as possible. The selection of criteria to source the secondary data was based on the outcome of the InvestCEC kick-off consortium meeting at Magdalensberg in November 2022. The preliminary understanding of the segregation of industries and verticals Stadtwerke Klagenfurt is operating in was used as a basis to conduct this research. Furthermore, only active companies based in the European Union were recognized. The companies were subsequently grouped in the following categories:

- *Green technology and sustainability*
- *Renewable Energy*
- *Water purification*

- *Collaborative economy*
- *Waste management*
- *Car sharing*

Within these categories, all companies that met the criteria were included in the research. On this basis, the following data were analysed:

- *Sector/Category*
- *Age*
- *Amount of financing*
- *Blurb (qualitative and brief description of the business model)*
- *Stage of the company according to the title of the investment round, the age, and the amount of funding*
- *Geographical location of headquarters*
- *Investors*

This overview of companies will in subsequent internal InvestCEC analysis be combined with other companies or entrepreneurial initiatives identified through other sources by VENCAP. VENCAP screens a sustained inflow of >2,500 startup applications per year – including a share of CE cases – leveraging 13+ years of investing and advisory experience and a pan-European network of founders, corporates and co-investors.

Overview results & STW AG selection of high priority areas

Inspired by the wealth of information provided on the 680 companies analysed, STW AG has decided, when combining with their own needs analysis, that the most relevant “problem” areas where STW AG has identified the greatest needs are the following:

- *Green technology and sustainability*
- *Renewable energy*
- *Waste management*
- *Water purification*

Annex I of this document contains a selection of companies belonging to these 4 final categories, but the results are summarized below.

Figure 9. Summary of the result of the market analysis

Of the 680 companies and startups analysed, more than a third can be classified under Renewable Energy, around a fourth are classified under the Sustainability category, and only a tenth fall under Green Tech or Waste Management. However, there is some overlap, as is the case with entities that fall under both the Green Tech and Sustainability categories.

5.2.1. TEMPLATE FOR CITIES/REGIONS

This template was completed using the information presented by STW AG during the Kick-off Meeting of the InvestCEC project. It reflects the city’s initial needs definition, strategic objectives, and priority areas for CE development. The data provided by STW AG served as a reference case for testing and validating the InvestCEC model’s Needs Definition and Solution Identification stages.

The completed template outlines Klagenfurt’s vision, targets, and planned CE initiatives, which guided subsequent activities in the selection of relevant solution providers and entrepreneurs. This structured approach ensured that the pilot demonstration was fully aligned with the city’s climate strategy and circular transition priorities.

Table 4. Template for cities/regions

GENERAL INFORMATION

City/Municipality	Klagenfurt am Wörthersee
Location (region it is part of)	Carinthia, Austria
Name of municipal organization	Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG
Please provide links to city websites for more information	https://www.stw.at/
GENERAL VISION, TARGETS & STRATEGIES	
VISION What is the vision of your city/region	The Smart City Klagenfurt am Wörthersee will be an emission-neutral, energy-efficient, and resource-conserving living space with a high urban quality of life and responsible citizens, which is well integrated with the Alps-Adriatic region.
TARGETS What targets have been set to work to follow this vision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Achieving balancing climate neutrality by 2030.</i> – <i>In the initial situation based on 2011, greenhouse gas emissions of around 734.000 tons were calculated for the urban area. These emissions have already been reduced by -49% by 2018 and -54% by 2021. The remaining 335.000 to are to be reduced to -81% (194.000 to) by 2030 with the implementation of key measures and the remaining -19% (141.000 to) offset with compensation measures.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase modal Split in public transportation ○ Provide sustainable and affordable energy ○ Active participation of citizens

	<div style="text-align: right;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Calculations according to the COM method (Covenant of Mayors)</p> <p>Figure source: Dr. Wolfgang Hafner, Climate and environmental protection department of STW AG „Presentation „Pathway to climate neutrality 2030“.</p>
<p>STRATEGIES</p> <p>What measures and strategies have been set to achieve these targets</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substitute natural gas and oil with renewables • Make biogenic waste available for biogas production: e.g. heat production or as fuel • Maximize the yield of biogas • Improve waste management systems to harness the value of waste • Optimization of the municipal wastewater treatment plant
<p>Other measures discussed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 9 working groups, experts developed measures and projects for implementation for each individual field of action, which are listed in an annex. This appendix is to be understood as a working aid and serves as support and orientation for the implementation of the Smart City Climate Strategy of Klagenfurt. Measures and projects with financial implications must be submitted to the political bodies after detailed planning and review of technical and financial feasibility and finally for resolution.
<p>STRENGTHS</p> <p>Regional Strengths and resources available</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good inter-municipal cooperation • Good cooperation with Associations in Austria and other platforms • Cooperation with the University of Klagenfurt • Active participation in various working groups • Active participation of the citizens of Klagenfurt
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>What resources are less present and could</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative solutions for material management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collect ○ Sort ○ Treatment ○ Delivering

<p>serve to realize the city's vision</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cogeneration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ New technologies ○ exhaust air purification ○ Innovative coating of boilers ○ Combine with H2
<p>CIRCULAR ECONOMY ACHIEVEMENTS</p> <p>Do you have any existing or past examples of circular economy projects or initiatives in your city/region?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KEBIP - Klagenfurt Bus Infrastructure Project https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20220297
<p>PLANNED PROJECT 1</p>	
<p>NAME</p>	<p>Heat production through recycling-measures</p>
<p>LEAD</p>	<p>Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG - Segment Leader "energy production"</p>
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Project Description</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heat-production with waste management cycle - Recycling of residuals, plywood, and furniture
<p>TASKS</p> <p>Projects actions/tasks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of sorting plant • Construction of a power-heat-coupling fluidized bed oven • Connection to existing district heating and power grid
<p>BUDGET</p>	<p>Investment volume 2024-2026: €50M</p>
<p>STAKEHOLDERS</p> <p>Who are the stakeholders and</p>	<p>Waste management plants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collect - sort - treatment - delivering

<p>actors in this project, what are their role</p>	<p>District heating plants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - handle high-energy-waste - manage power-heat-coupling-process - power generation, heat generation <p>District heating grid:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of heat to the customer
<p>RESSOURCES</p> <p>Strengths of project: actors, technology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear smart-city-strategy • Massive changes in energy market prices • Price stability due to existing sustainable heat production in Klagenfurt • Increasing market demand • Existing inter-municipal co-operation
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>Missing elements / actors / technology/ supply chain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of local waste flows • Localizing the usable mass • Identifying the types of best types of waste • Determining the optimal dimension and technology of waste combustion
<p>MIRROR PROJECTS</p> <p>Examples of successful similar/inspiring solutions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy center “Forsthaus” - Bern (Switzerland) - As a complete system, the Forsthaus energy center converts waste, regional wood and natural gas into electricity, steam, and district heating. (https://www.ewb.ch/ueberuns/unternehmen/kraftwerke/energiezentrale-forsthaus.php)
<p>CIRCULARITY</p> <p>How does the solution in question qualify as circular? E.g.:</p> <p><u>“Eliminates waste and pollution”</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eliminates waste and pollution • Circulate products and materials at their highest value • Substitution of gas and oil • Regenerate nature

“Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)”

“Regenerate nature”

BUTTERFLY DIAGRAM

Does the solution’s value chain operate on the technical or biological side of the butterfly diagram? (explain)

Can you place your solution on the butterfly diagram? Please explain

PLANNED PROJECT 2

NAME

Extraction of green gas from sludge

LEAD

- Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG - Segment Manager “Gas”
- City of Klagenfurt – Department Manager “Waste and Wastewater Services”

DESCRIPTION

Project Description

- Incineration of sewage sludge
- Sludge incineration for the production of waste heat

<p>TASKS</p> <p>Projects actions/tasks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of a biogas plant as part of the planned renewal of the existing wastewater treatment plant • Connection to the existing district gas grid • Setting up storage facilities • Adaptation of filling stations
<p>BUDGET</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Investment volume 2024-2026: €20M</i>
<p>STAKEHOLDERS</p> <p>Who are the stakeholders and actors in this project, what are their role</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Politically responsible persons - Decision of principles</i> – <i>Department Manager “Environmental Protection” - Coordinator Smart City Strategy</i> – <i>Department Manager “Waste and wastewater services”</i>
<p>RESSOURCES</p> <p>Strengths of project: actors, technology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear smart-city-strategy • Massive changes in energy market prices • Existing inter-municipal co-operation
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>Missing elements / actors / technology/ supply chain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasibility study • Technical and commercial studies
<p>MIRROR PROJECTS</p> <p>Examples of successful similar/inspiring solutions</p>	

<p>CIRCULARITY</p> <p>How does the solution in question qualify as circular? E.g.:</p> <p><u>“Eliminates waste and pollution”</u></p> <p><u>“Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)”</u></p> <p><u>“Regenerate nature”</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eliminate waste and pollution • Circulate products and materials at their highest value • Regenerate nature
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<p>BUTTERFLY DIAGRAM</p> <p>Does the solution’s value chain operate on the technical or biological side of the <u>butterfly diagram</u>? (explain)</p>	<p>RENEWABLES FLOW MANAGEMENT RENEWABLES FINITE MATERIALS STOCK MANAGEMENT</p> <p>FARMING/COLLECTION¹ PARTS MANUFACTURER RECYCLE</p> <p>BIOCHEMICAL FEEDSTOCK PRODUCT MANUFACTURER REFURBISH/REMANUFACTURE</p> <p>REGENERATION BIOSPHERE SERVICE PROVIDER SHARE MAINTAIN/PROLONG REUSE/REDISTRIBUTE</p> <p>BIOGAS ANAEROBIC DIGESTION CASCADES CONSUMER USER COLLECTION COLLECTION</p> <p>EXTRACTION OF BIOCHEMICAL FEEDSTOCK² MINIMISE SYSTEMATIC LEAKAGE AND NEGATIVE EXTERNALITIES</p> <p><small>SOURCE: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Circular economy systems diagram (February 2019), www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org. Drawing based on Braungart & McDonough, Cradle to Cradle (C2C).</small></p> <p style="text-align: right;">ELLEN MACARTHUR FOUNDATION</p> <p><i>Can you place your solution on the butterfly diagram? Please explain</i></p>
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PLANNED PROJECT 3	
NAME	Green gas production from biomass waste

<p>LEAD</p>	<p>Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG – Segment Manager “Gas”</p> <p>City of Klagenfurt – Department Manager “Waste Services”</p>
<p>DESCRIPTION</p> <p>Project Description</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Combined fermentation & composting plant for organic waste first produces methane and then produces compost and fertilizer The compost is produced in intensive rotting boxes.</i> – <i>The plant is equipped with a hygienization device for the percolating water. The system in boxes with the batch operation is perfect for continuous biogas production.</i> – <i>Biomethane is fed into the gas grid, the fresh compost is made available to the surrounding farmers and collected by private individuals, the percolate that is produced is hygienized and can be used as liquid fertilizer. The plant is expandable.</i>
<p>TASKS</p> <p>Projects actions/tasks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing an efficient collection process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gastronomy ○ Commercial ○ Composting-plants • Construction of a biogas-gasification plant • Connection to the existing gas grid, setting up storage facilities, adaptation of filling stations
<p>BUDGET</p>	<p>Investment volume 2024-2026: €10M</p>
<p>STAKEHOLDERS</p> <p>Who are the stakeholders and actors in this project, what are their role</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Politically responsible persons - Decision of principles</i> – <i>Department Manager “Environmental Protection” - Coordinator Smart City Strategy</i> – <i>Department Manager “Waste and wastewater services”</i> – <i>Supervisory Board of Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG</i> – <i>Approval of the investment proposal of the Management Board.</i> – <i>Management Board of Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG</i> – <i>Approval investment application</i>
<p>RESSOURCES</p> <p>Strengths of project: actors, technology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing inter-municipal cooperation in the region of Carinthia • Working groups of the Austrian Association of Cities.

<p>NEEDS</p> <p>Missing elements / actors / technology/ supply chain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasibility study • Technical and commercial studies • Analyses of supply chain (Integral business processes) • Software support for integral business processes
<p>MIRROR PROJECTS</p> <p>Examples of successful similar/inspiring solutions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biogas plant – Udine (Italy)
<p>CIRCULARITY</p> <p>How does the solution in question qualify as circular? E.g.:</p> <p><u>“Eliminates waste and pollution”</u></p> <p><u>“Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)”</u></p> <p><u>“Regenerate nature”</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eliminates waste and pollution • Circulate products and materials at their highest value • Regenerate nature

BUTTERFLY DIAGRAM

Does the solution's value chain operate on the technical or biological side of the butterfly diagram? (explain)

Can you place your solution on the butterfly diagram? Please explain

5.2.2. TEMPLATE FOR ENTREPRENEURS

This template has been completed using information (highlighted in green) collected from the publicly available website of Aquagreen,¹⁰ one of the companies identified in the market analysis conducted by VENCAP, a partner in the InvestCEC project, based on data sourced from Crunchbase.com. The information was compiled without direct contact with the company and therefore serves solely as an illustrative example for demonstrating the application of the template.

COMPANY INFO	
NAME	AquaGreen

¹⁰ This template has been completed using information (highlighted in green) collected from the publicly available website of Aquagreen, one of the companies identified in the market analysis conducted by VENCAP, a partner in the InvestCEC project, based on data sourced from Crunchbase.com. The information was compiled without direct contact with the company and therefore serves solely as an illustrative example for demonstrating the application of the template. However, it is important to note that G2G contacted Aquagreen and confirmed that the company's solution is not relevant for Austria due to national restrictions on the use of even eco-friendly biochar containing nutrients.

LOCATION	Roskilde, Denmark
WEBSITE	https://aquagreen.dk/
FIELD Please describe your general expertise and current operations	AquaGreen is a Danish engineering company within cleantech.
ACHIEVEMENTS	backed by various investors hereunder the Danish Workers Pension Fund (ATP), developed and patented with the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), and recognized by innovation awards.
YOUR SOLUTION	
NAME	Turn your waste into resources
DESCRIPTION Please provide a short description of your project	INTEGRATED STEAM-DRYING AND PYROLYSIS Fully automated, continuous process With AquaGreen’s HECLA® 1,000 plant, you can treat 1,000 metric tons of dry matter annually. Doing so, will reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 1,800 tons CO2e, produce 2,000 MWh of sustainable energy, and store 500 ton of carbon in biochar. The resulting biochar is odorless and has a content of 5-6% plant-accessible phosphorus.
VALUE CHAIN Describe the value chain of your solution	Wastewater is produced and contains sludge (106K tons in DK in 2028). The sludge is separated into utility plants. The sludge is treated with steam dryers and a pyrolysis oven to remove microplastics, medicine residues, and heavy metals. This produces eco-friendly biochar full of nutrients. The biochar is sold to farmers and nutrients reintroduced to the ground, or can also be used in other treatment plants as activated carbon for water purification
STAKEHOLDERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens: produce sludge • Utility plants: waste-water management • AquaGreen: deliver and service technology • Municipal organization/partnerships: sell and distribute biochar • Farmers: buy biochar as environmentally friendly fertilizer

<p>Please list the stakeholders, their roles and interests</p>	
<p>YOUR ROLE</p> <p>What is your role in this value chain?</p>	<p>Aquagreen can provide the technology and service it. They can also help design the right solutions tailored to the specific requirements of the utility plant in question.</p>
<p>STRENGTHS</p> <p>Please describe the strengths of your solution. What do you think will make it successful?</p>	<p>Solid technology with proven through installations in Sweden and Denmark.</p>
<p>NEEDS</p> <p>Are there any missing elements, or elements that could be strengthened?</p>	<p>Knowledge and partnerships to define and adapt to the needs of Klagenfurt</p>
<p>DEVELOPMENT STAGE</p>	
<p>PROGRESS</p> <p>Please describe the current state of development of your solution</p>	<p>Technology is fully developed and ready to be installed for a project tailored to the city's needs.</p>

<p>FINANCIAL NEEDS</p> <p>Please provide an estimate of the investments needed to bring your solution to maturity</p>	<p>The tech costs xxx € per Ton of sludge capacity.</p>
<p>TIMELINE</p> <p>How long would it take to develop and deploy your solution?</p>	<p>The Aquagreen technology can be produced and set up within x months/years.</p>
<p>INNOVATION & CIRCULARITY</p>	
<p>REFERENCE PROJECTS</p> <p>Have you or any of the partners created/participated in other similar projects? Are you inspired by any other projects?</p>	<p>Sludge treatment plant attracts great interest</p> <p>In an interview with sn.dk, the CEO of Odsherred Forsyning, Fanny Villadsen, states that the interest in their newly installed steam-drying and pyrolysis plant has been great. They have had more than 450 visitors during the last 12 months who wanted to see the plant and hear more about the technology.</p> <p>The plant has been installed at the Fårevejle wastewater treatment plant and handles all the sludge from the municipality's 50,000 households.</p>
<p>INNOVATION</p> <p>How does your solution differ from existing solutions?</p>	<p>Sludge is currently used directly on fields and fertilizer, and contains harmful elements for the soil (microplastics...). Aquagreen's technology produces clean and environmentally friendly biochar.</p>
<p>CIRCULARITY</p> <p>How does the solution in question qualify as circular? E.g.:</p>	<p>Our solution offers a way to "Eliminate and pollution" by valorizing sludge and reintroducing it to the soil without the harmful substances.</p>

“Eliminates waste and pollution”

“Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)”

“Regenerate nature”

It also offers a contribution to “regenerate nature”, as the biochar produced allows to reintroduce of nutrients from sludge into the ground without using artificial/chemical fertilizer.

BUTTERFLY DIAGRAM

Does the solution’s value chain operate on the technical or biological side of the **butterfly diagram**? (explain)

The solution fits on the biological cycle (left-hand side) of the butterfly diagram, by offering a way to farm with positive outcomes for nature by contributing to:

- *healthy and stable soils,*
- *improved air and water quality,*
- *and storing more carbon in the soil.*

ness

The Investment Readiness stage of the InvestCEC model was tested and validated in Klagenfurt am Wörthersee, focusing on transforming locally identified CE projects into investment-ready business cases. This stage was led by G2G in close cooperation with VENCAP, STW AG, and the City of Klagenfurt, supported by inputs from external experts and local stakeholders.

Following the needs definition and selection process, several priority projects were identified in Klagenfurt, with a particular focus on circular bioenergy and waste valorisation value chains. The investment readiness activities concentrated on two core areas:

1. **Wastewater and Sewage Sludge Valorisation** – development of a sewage sludge incineration and waste heat recovery plant integrated with the existing wastewater treatment facility. The goal was to convert biogenic waste into renewable energy, produce usable heat for district heating, and recover nutrients for agricultural use.
2. **Organic Waste and Biogas Production** – planning of a new organic waste treatment plant to process approximately 15,000 tonnes of organic waste per year, producing biogas, compost, and fertiliser while supporting the city's transition to renewable gas for households.

Investment Readiness Support and Tools

Entrepreneurs and municipal representatives participating in the Klagenfurt pilot were introduced to the G2G Business Plan Tool, made available for InvestCEC to support the creation of high-quality, investment-ready business plans. The tool includes:

- An online business plan writer,
- A budget and financial forecasting module, and
- A self-assessment/quality assessment function to evaluate completeness and consistency.

These tools were offered to participants in turning project concepts into bankable investment cases by developing clear narratives, and realistic implementation strategies in a model. During the pilot, STW AG applied this structured approach to document project assumptions, expected circular and financial outcomes, and potential funding pathways.

Evaluation and Alignment with Investors

The developed project cases were reviewed and discussed with VENCAP, which applied the InvestCEC investor evaluation framework, covering business model innovation, scalability, technological maturity, financial viability, and circular impact. Feedback from VENCAP and external experts helped refine project documentation to better align with investor expectations and ESG standards.

The exercise demonstrated that municipal circular projects can be effectively prepared for private investment, provided that technical and economic data are presented in investor-compatible formats. It also confirmed the importance of early integration between public project developers and private investors to ensure funding alignment and accelerate implementation.

At the same time, several systemic barriers became clear. Municipal circular initiatives typically operate on long time scales, with amortisation periods of 10 to 30 years, involve multiple public stakeholders, and generate

environmental and social value that is not always monetised. These can contrast with the expectations of traditional private investors, who favour predictable returns, scalable revenue models, and clear exit strategies. Further complications arise from public procurement procedures and tendering rules, which are often unfamiliar or incompatible with private investment processes, creating delays or limiting partnership models such as PPPs. Additionally, municipal projects may be subject to shifting regulatory frameworks—such as changing tax rules, environmental standards, or political priorities, which increase perceived risk from an investor's perspective.

As a result, circular infrastructure projects led by municipalities may appear less attractive to traditional investors, who typically prioritise predictable returns, scalable business models, and clear exit strategies. This creates a clear need for intermediaries who can bridge institutional and cultural gaps. Intermediaries capable of translating public-sector requirements into market-compatible business models and structuring investments that satisfy both public service mandates and private return expectations.

In this context, InvestCEC played a facilitating role. By serving as an intermediary between municipal actors and private investors, the initiative contributed to aligning public-sector priorities with investment-oriented concepts and informed project developers about the expectations and concerns of private financiers.

amme

For the Klagenfurt demonstration, VENCAP designed a financing architecture that is both prepared for fund establishment and already usable via partner co-investment.

Following a delayed cornerstone commitment for the InvestCEC EuVECA/AIF, VENCAP pursued a dual track: (i) continue cornerstone-first fundraising and (ii) stand up an alternative venture-partnership (“virtual fund”) pathway that enables joint screening, diligence and co-investment with aligned VC managers and strategic investors. Several fundraising routes were tested—direct cornerstone outreach (after an initial industrial lead withdrew), a Fund-of-Funds concept with a large German investment manager, and targeted strategic LPs. In parallel, VENCAP finalised the legal/operational mechanics for the venture-partnership model and prepared a crowd co-investment rail with CONDA/European Super Angels Club; this infrastructure is now ready to use once the AIF is registered. The co-investment rail is live for ESAC syndications today and can be connected after registration. Given market headwinds (longer cycles for first-time/thematic funds, reduced risk appetite, CE seen by parts of the market as quasi-public remit, and limited precedent for industrial LPs in micro-funds), VENCAP concentrated on building a bankable pipeline and “ready-to-run” processes so qualified cases can progress via partner co-investment now and through the InvestCEC AIF once a cornerstone is secured. FMA registration has a prepared dossier and can be executed rapidly post-cornerstone. Standing up this coalition and co-investment mechanics with VC partners and strategic investors—required additional legal and operational work, so it reached a ready-to-run state only toward the end of the project.

The Dedicated EuVECA/AIF is prepared: A European venture vehicle managed by Venionaire Capital has been fully prepared to finance utility-ready circular-economy ventures. Formal registration will be triggered once a cornerstone LP is secured. The documentation set (all legal registration documents, Investment Focus & Fund Facts, Pitch Deck, LP Questionnaire/subscription set, governance/compliance) and impact instrumentation are in place and aligned with project materials.

The Venture-partnership model (“virtual fund”): In parallel, the programme operates through a venture-partnership model that enables joint screening, diligence, and co-investment with aligned managers and strategic investors. The core partners include **Una Terra** (early-growth impact) and **Universe Partners** (resilience tech); additional strategic capacity and co-investments could be provided by the **Carinthian Venture Fund (CVF)** and a **major electricity provider with its venture arm**. This coalition broadens ticket flexibility, sector coverage, and follow-on strength so qualified cases can progress ahead of—and later alongside—the AIF’s first close.

After fund establishment, a crowd co-investment track via **CONDA** (together with the **European Super Angels Club**) could broaden participation for private investors and citizens on a deal-by-deal basis.

How this supports the demonstration. Opportunity sourcing is fed by the two Calls for Entrepreneurs and Venionaire’s pan-European deal flow. Short-listed teams enter a standardised investment-readiness pathway and are assessed with **STW-AG** for utility deployability. Aligned cases are then shared with venture partners for joint diligence and potential co-investment.

Standards and transparency. The investment programme integrates circular-economy criteria and ESG indicators into screening and due diligence, and provides practical guidance for portfolio management and impact monitoring (in line with project guidelines). This produces comparable, decision-useful materials for municipalities and investors and supports replication across regions.

The investment program shows that a PPP-anchored venture-partnership (“virtual fund”) approach is viable. It can mobilise capital pathways for circular solutions before a market is ready to cornerstone a thematic fund, while simultaneously building a pipeline that is ready once the vehicle launches. Although tailored to the context, the logic is replicable: pair broad-mandate partner funds with regional or sector-specific investors, add strategic industrial partnerships, and coordinate through a transparent, utility-aligned funnel. Together, this coalition could unlock more potential, accelerate PPP deployment, and scale the circular economy across cities and regions.

6. Conclusions

The **InvestCEC project** has developed a comprehensive, practical, and transferable model for transforming local CE ambitions into investable projects. Through the integration of technical guidance, stakeholder collaboration, and innovative financing models, the project bridges the gap between municipal needs and market-based investment logic.

The **Klagenfurt demonstration** has proven that the model is applicable in real-world urban contexts. It showed that municipalities can lead complex circular transitions when equipped with clear methodologies, transparent selection processes, and structured support in developing investment-ready projects. The collaboration between **STW AG**, and **VENCAP** established a replicable workflow— from needs identification to investment activation— grounded in both environmental and financial performance to be continued beyond the EU project.

Key conclusions include:

- The structured **templates and selection criteria** ensure consistency and replicability across European regions.
- The **G2G Business Plan Tool** effectively improves investment readiness for circular ventures and facilitates engagement with investors.
- The combination of municipal leadership, entrepreneurial innovation, and financial expertise is essential for successful circular transition implementation.

The InvestCEC model now provides a **tested framework and toolset** ready for adoption by other European cities and regions. It supports the EU's **Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan**, and **Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities**, contributing to the acceleration of Europe's transition toward a circular, resource-efficient, and climate-neutral economy.